

Clusters of agrosystems data in accordance with relevant legal categories

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Abstract

Data can be sensitive for ethical, data protection, economic or other reasons. The result includes 18 Research data infrastructures (RDI) covering different aspects of datasets. As a result we suggest adding information about licensing and access of the data to the metadata of each dataset and an access concept for sensitive datasets.

Research question and Methods

At the beginning of the study, the situation of the research data infrastructure (RDI) in the community was still unclear. However, there was a list of RDIs that should be integrated, are required by the use cases (UC) or are otherwise important for the domain. This list was compiled by FAIRagro TA2 (Community Involvement and Networking) and individual participants from other task areas. Due to the limited knowledge about the status quo, open questions were asked. The list of questions for the known contacts of the RDIs included questions on the type of data, applicable standards and type of access restrictions, each as free text.

Results

The following RDIs responded:

ID (Repo list)	Institute	Name of RDI
1	Thünen Institute	TISDAR
2	Senckenberg	Edaphobase
3	ZALF	BonaRes Repository
4	IPK Gatersleben	GBIS/I
5	IPK Gatersleben	EDAL-PGP
6	JKI	OpenAgrar
7	ZB MED	PUBLISSO Repository for Life Sciences
8	Thünen Institute	Thünen Atlas
10	JKI	JKI-DataCube (formerly DaCuRa)
17	TUM	SRADI (UC SRADI4AGRI)
20	FZ Jülich	PlabiPD
21	KTBL	EmiMin/EmiDat
22	Senckenberg	FLOPOknb
29	Staatliche Archive Bayern	ACTApro
30	Uni Bonn	PhenoRoam
35	DWD	Open Data Server
36	ATB	ATB Research Data Catalogue
37	HSWT	Geo Data Server
38	HSWT	IoT Frontend

Responses were received or subsequently recorded from 18 infrastructures. The responses on the type of data confirmed the compilation determined so far and helped to understand the other responses. The responses on the applicable standards revealed legal uncertainties, but also made it easier to classify the other responses. The following clusters emerged from the free text responses to the question about restrictions on access:

- Public data / CC0 1.0 Universal / free access / Public Domain ...
 - GBIS/I
 - FLOPOknb
 - PhenoRoam
 - ATB Research Data Catalogue
- CC BY / License according to CreativeCommons / Open Database License / Good scientific practice ...
 - BonaRes Repository
 - EDAL-PGP
 - PUBLISSO Repository for Life Sciences
 - Open Data Server
 - ATB Research Data Catalogue
- CC BY-NC / non-commercial usage ...
 - Edaphobase
- Registrierung nötig ...
 - Edaphobase
 - ATB Research Data Catalogue
- Data on request / Embargo possible / (some) internal / application via E-Mail ...
 - TISDAR
 - Edaphobase
 - BonaRes Repository

13.06.2024

- o OpenAgrar
- o PUBLISSO Repository for Life Sciences
- o JKI-DataCube (formerly DaCuRa)
- o SRADI (UC SRADI4AGRI)
- o PlabiPD
- o ACTApro
- o ATB Research Data Catalogue
- o Geo Data Server
- o IoT Frontend
- not yet decided - nature of data however might suggest public domain except if/where DSGVO applies.
 - o EmiMin/EmiDat

The answers were included in the list of RDIs. As further findings are expected, it will be continued as a living document.

Evaluation

Although not all RDIs responded, it can be assumed that the 18 infrastructures represent the status quo of the community. This should provide a broad picture that covers the requirements of the system to be created. The presentation and discussion at a workshop confirmed this.

The response clusters resulted in the following suggestions for the metadata that the RDIs transmit to the FAIRagro middleware (Measure 4.2) for each dataset regarding the legal treatment of the dataset:

- How may the data be reused? (data usage license)
 - o Open
 - o Open with attribution (default)
 - o Non-commercial with attribution
- How can the data be accessed?
 - o Free (default)
 - o Logged in only (downloads can be tracked)
 - o On request (possibly with expiration date)

The proposal is that at least basic bibliographic metadata (scope and standardization determined by the relevant working groups) should be accessible for each dataset. This data is always freely accessible in order to make the dataset findable. The legal metadata determines how further data is output. To this end, FAIRagro must receive and store all data through the RDIs, but does not release it all to every user. The RDIs can decide whether they want this or whether the users should be forwarded to them. There will be a messaging system to request restricted data sets.

RDI	License			Access		
	Open	With attribution	Non-commercial with attribution	Free	Log in	On request
TISDAR						X
Edaphobase			X		X	X
BonaRes Repository		X		X		X
GBIS/I	X			X		
EDAL-PGP	X	X	X	X		
OpenAgrar				X		X
PUBLISSO Repository for Life Sciences		X		X		X
Thünen Atlas	X	X	X	X		X
JKI-DataCube (formerly DaCuRa)						X
SRADI (UC SRADI4AGRI)				X		X
PlabiPD				X		X
EmiMin/EmiDat	X					X
FLOPOknb	X					
ACTApro						X
PhenoRoam	X			X		
Open Data Server		X		X		
ATB Research Data Catalogue	X	X		X	X	X
Geo Data Server						X
IoT Frontend						X

No CC licenses have been proposed on purpose, but general descriptions have been given. The exact license that is legally possible and meets the necessary requirements is still being determined. Additional topics that emerged from the interviews are data protection and the Nagoya Protocol.

New questions on barriers to data publication to potential data providers and producers emerged from the responses and discussions. These will be put to the community in the form of a survey at the FAIRagro Community Summit.

The next steps are detailed discussions with the working groups for metadata, middleware and portal. There will be meetings with other NFDI consortia that are developing similar solutions.

Research funding

This work was created as part of the NFDI consortium FAIRagro (www.fairagro.net). We gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the German Research Foundation (DFG) – project number 501899475.